

Synthesis, spectral characterization and *in vitro* anti-inflammatory activity of 4-substituted amino-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines

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Abstract : A new series of 4-substituted amino-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines synthesized from 2-amino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiophene-3-carboxamide. Their structures were characterized by elemental analysis, UV, FTIR and ¹H NMR study. The entire compounds were screened for anti-inflammatory activity by *in vitro* method. All the compounds exhibited significant to moderate biological activities.

Keywords : Thiophenopyrimidine, tetrahydrobenzothiophene, *in vitro* anti-inflammatory activity.

Introduction

The thiopheno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine system is isosteric with several condensed system such as purine and quinazoline which has antimalarial and antihistaminic activity respectively^{1,2}. Recently this has led to the extensive investigation of benzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines which has anti-inflammatory activity³⁻⁸. Based on these observations the present investigation is designed. The starting compound was prepared by a method developed by Gewald^{9,10} as a special case of asinger reaction¹¹ from cyclohexanone, cyanoacetamide and sulphur. Cyclization and chlorination gives the corresponding compounds¹². Conversions of this into various new pyrimidines were done by using appropriate synthetic route¹³⁻¹⁵.

Results and discussion

The synthetic routes of targeted compounds were done from starting compound 2-amino-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenzothiophene-3-carboxamide. The detail scheme is represented. All the compounds synthesized were adequately characterized by their elemental analysis and spectroscopic techniques.

Chemistry :

It is well established that reaction of available cyclo-

hexanone, cyanoacetamide and powdered sulphur with diethylamine and absolute alcohol yields compound 1 which was followed by cyclization by heating with formamide produced compound 2. Compound 2 on chlorination with phosphorous oxychloride yields compound 3. It was treated with different amines such as aromatic, allyl and secondary amines in presence of absolute ethanol to give target compounds 4(a-h) (Scheme 1).

Anti-inflammatory activity :

All new synthesized compounds were screened for *in vitro* anti-inflammatory activity using inhibition of albumin denaturation technique¹⁶ which was studied according to Mizushima and Kobayashi with slight modification¹⁷. Dimethyl formamide (DMF) was used as solvent. No drug was added as control. Each experiment was done in triplicate and average was taken. Ibuprofen was used as standard drug. All the compounds screened for *in vitro* anti-inflammatory activity exhibited significant to moderate result. Compound *N*-cyclohexyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (4e) showed highest percentage of denaturation as compare to standard ibuprofen. Result of anti-inflammatory activity is tabulated (Table 1).

Fig. 1. General scheme for synthesis of 4-substituted amino-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2,3-d]pyrimidines 4(a-h).

Table 1. *In vitro* anti-inflammatory activity of compounds 4(a-h)

Comps.	Absorbance value (Mean ± SE)	Inhibition of denaturation (in %)
Control	0.098 ± 0.007	-
Ibuprofen	0.182 ± 0.002	85.71
4a	0.120 ± 0.004	22.44
4b	0.123 ± 0.004	25.51
4c	0.137 ± 0.005	39.79
4d	0.131 ± 0.008	33.67
4e	0.164 ± 0.005	67.34
4f	0.151 ± 0.001	54.08
4g	0.141 ± 0.003	43.87
4h	0.124 ± 0.006	26.53

Experimental

General :

All commercial reagents and chemicals were used without further purification. Reactions were monitored by TLC. Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded by a Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectrometer Bruker Vertex 70 equipped with an attenuated total reflection (ATR) accessory with a diamond crystal. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AM 400 instrument (at 400 MHz) using tetramethyl silane (TMS) as an internal standard and CDCl₃ as a solvent. The ¹H

NMR chemical shift values (δ) are expressed in ppm referred to tetramethyl silane (TMS). Mass spectra were recorded on Shimadzu GC MS QP 5000.

Precoated Merck Silica Gel 60F-254 plates were used for thin layer chromatography (TLC) and the spots were detected under UV light (254 nm). Elemental analyses were carried out using FLASH EA 1112 CHN analyzer from Thermo Finnigen, Italy and values were within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the calculated.

Chemistry :

Specific examples presented below illustrate general synthetic procedure.

2-Amino-4, 5, 6, 7-tetrahydrobenzothiophene-3-carboxamide (**1**) :

A mixture of cyclohexanone (0.1 mol), cyanoacetamide (0.1 mol) and powdered sulphur (0.11 mol) was stirred together with diethylamine (15 ml) and absolute alcohol (20 ml) to get yellow precipitate of compound **1**. (40.41%) m.p. 160 °C (d) (Found : C, 54.86; H, 6.14; N, 13.36. Calcd. for $C_9H_{12}N_2OS$ (196.30) : C, 55.16; H, 6.24; N, 14.36%).

5, 6, 7, 8-Tetrahydro-3H-benzothiopheno[2, 3-d]pyrimidin-4-one (**2**) :

A suspension of compound (**1**) (0.0102 mol) in freshly distilled formamide (15 ml) was heated in an oil bath at 170 °C till the evolution of ammonia vapors. Yellow needles recrystallised with aqueous alcohol. (55.81%) m.p. 154 °C (d) (Found : C, 57.12; H, 4.56; N, 13.39. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_{10}N_2OS$ (206.33) : C, 58.22; H, 4.90; N, 13.69%).

4-Chloro-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2, 3-d]pyrimidine (**3**) :

A suspension of compound (**2**) (0.01 mol) in phosphorous oxychloride (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 9 h to get colorless lump. (71.31%) m.p. 177 °C (d) (Found : C, 53.12; H, 4.01; N, 12.39. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_9ClN_2S$ (224.70) : C, 53.51; H, 4.00; N, 12.55%).

N-Phenyl-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2, 3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (**4a**) :

A mixture of compound (**3**) (0.002 mol) and aniline (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under gentle reflux to yield derivative **4a**. (72.11%) m.p. 180 °C (d) (Found : C, 67.99; H, 5.35; N, 14.88. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{15}N_3S$: C, 68.33; H, 5.41; N, 14.90%); v_{max} :

3420 (NH), 1570 (C=N), 1460 (C=C), 669 (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 1.57–2.67 (8H, m, C5,C6,C7,C8), 7.21–7.97 (5H, m, C2',C3',C4',C5',C6'; Ar-H); EI-MS : m/z 281 (M^+).

N-(p-Tolyl)-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2, 3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (**4b**) :

A mixture of compound (**3**) (0.002 mol) and 4-methylaniline (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under gentle reflux to yield derivative **4b**. (78.00%) m.p. 132 °C (d) (Found : C, 68.89; H, 5.80; N, 14.19. Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{17}N_3S$: C, 69.17; H, 5.87; N, 14.23%); v_{max} : 3445 (NH), 1585 (C=N), 1485 (C=C), 643 (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.60–2.58 (8H, m, C5,C6,C7,C8), 7.69–8.06 (5H, m, C2',C3',C4',C5',C6'; Ar-H), 1.37 (3H, t, $-CH_3$); EI-MS : m/z 295 (M^+).

N-Propyl-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2, 3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (**4c**) :

A mixture of compound (**3**) (0.002 mol) and propanamine (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under gentle reflux to yield derivative **4c**. (83.10%) m.p. 97 °C (d) (Found : C, 63.10; H, 6.82; N, 17.04. Calcd. for $C_{13}H_{17}N_3S$: C, 63.17; H, 6.90; N, 17.11%); v_{max} : 3420 (NH), 1550 (C=N), 1465 (C=C), 651 (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 1.57–2.67 (8H, m, C5,C6,C7,C8), 1.45 (3H, t, $-CH_3$), 4.37 (4H, t, $-CH_2$); EI-MS : m/z 275 (M^+).

N-Butyl-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2, 3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (**4d**) :

A mixture of compound (**3**) (0.002 mol) and butanamine (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under gentle reflux to yield derivative **4d**. (88.00%) m.p. 170 °C (d) (Found : C, 64.21; H, 7.28; N, 16.09. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{19}N_3S$: C, 64.30; H, 7.31; N, 16.15%); v_{max} : 3480 (NH), 1600 (C=N), 1480 (C=C), 662 (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 1.67–2.54 (8H, m, C5,C6,C7,C8), 1.42 (3H, t, $-CH_3$), 4.27 (6H, t, $-CH_2$); EI-MS : m/z 261 (M^+).

N-Cyclohexyl-5, 6, 7, 8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2, 3-d]pyrimidin-4-amine (**4e**) :

A mixture of compound (**3**) (0.002 mol) and cyclohexanamine (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under gentle reflux to yield derivative **4e**. (70.25%) m.p. 125 °C (d) (Found : C, 66.00; H, 7.24; N, 14.55. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{21}N_3S$: C, 66.90; H, 7.40; N, 14.63%); v_{max} : 3465 (NH), 1585 (C=N), 1460 (C=C), 666 (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 1.44–2.54 (9H, m, C5,C6,C7,C8,

C2',C3',C4',C5', C6'); EI-MS : m/z 287 (M^+).

N,N-Diethyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-4-amine (**4f**) :

A mixture of compound (**3**) (0.002 mol) and *N,N*-diethylamine (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under gentle reflux to yield derivative **4f**. (80.34%) m.p. 82 °C (d) (Found : C, 64.11; H, 7.12; N, 15.89. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{19}N_3S$: C, 64.30; H, 7.32; N, 16.11%); v_{max} : 1600, 1550 (C=N), 1500, 1460 (C=C), 643 (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 1.57–2.64 (4H, m, C5,C6,C7,C8), 1.45 (6H, t, $-CH_3$), 4.37 (4H, t, $-CH_2$); EI-MS : m/z 261 (M^+).

4-(1-Piperidyl)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidine (**4g**) :

A mixture of compound (**3**) (0.002 mol) and piperidine (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under gentle reflux to yield derivative **4g**. (89.14%) m.p. 90 °C (d) (Found : C, 65.34; H, 7.04; N, 15.40. Calcd. for $C_{15}H_{19}N_3S$: C, 65.90; H, 7.00; N, 15.44%); v_{max} : 1580, 1550 (C=N), 1480, 1380 (C=C), 671 (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 1.57–2.66 (4H, m, C5,C6,C7,C8), 1.44–2.74 (5H, m, C2',C3',C4',C5',C6'); EI-MS : m/z 273 (M^+).

4-(5,6,7,8-Tetrahydrobenzothiopheno[2,3-*d*]pyrimidin-4-yl)morpholine (**4h**) :

A mixture of compound (**3**) (0.002 mol) and morpholine (0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was heated under gentle reflux to yield derivative **4h**. (72.31%) m.p. 80 °C (d) (Found : C, 61.00; H, 6.21; N, 15.00. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{17}N_3OS$: C, 61.18; H, 6.25; N, 15.34); v_{max} : 1540, 1580 (C=N), 1420, 1365 (C=C), 653 (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 1.51–2.69 (4H, m, C5,C6,C7,C8), 3.51–3.90 (4H, m, C2',C3',C5',C6'); EI-MS : m/z 275 (M^+).

Anti-inflammatory activity :

The standard drug and test compounds were dissolved in minimum quantity of dimethyl formamide (DMF) and diluted with phosphate buffer (0.2 M, pH 7.4). Final concentration of DMF in all solution was less than 2.5%. Test solution (1 ml) containing different concentrations of drug was mixed with 1 ml of 1 mM albumin solution in phosphate buffer and incubated at 27 ± 1 °C in BOD incubator for 15 min. Denaturation was induced by keeping the reaction mixture at 60 ± 1 °C in water bath for 10 min. After cooling, the turbidity was measured at 660 nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer SL-159, Elico

India Ltd. The percentage inhibition of denaturation was calculated by using following formula.

$$\% \text{ of Inhibition} = 100 \times \{V_t/V_c - 1\}$$

where, V_t = mean absorbance of test sample, V_c = mean absorbance of control.

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